

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN IDIOM AND PHRASE AND THEIR USAGE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the different aspects of idioms and phrases and talks about their usage in English and Uzbek languages.

Keywords: idiom, phrase, different aspects, term, linguistics, fixed expressions, phraseologisms.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada idioma va frazalarning farqli jihatlari tahlil qilinadi va ularning ingliz va so'zzbek tillarida qso'zllanilish uslublari haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit sso'zlar: idioma, ibora, termin, tilshunoslik, turg'un iboralar, frazeologizmlar.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье анализируются различные аспекты идиом и фраз и рассказывается об их использовании в английском и узбекском языках.

Ключевые слова: идиома, словосочетание, разные аспекты, термин, языкознание, устойчивые выражения, фразеологизмы.

INTRODUCTION

The terms ‘idioms’ and ‘phrases’ are useful elements of linguistics, and are often considered similar. An Idiom and Phrase is basically a collection of words that are stuck together to behave more like a metaphor. These words help to change the meaning of the sentence. They make sentences, text, and speech more colorful. Idioms are fixed expressions that have a figurative meaning. They cannot directly be understood by just reading every single word of the sentence, one has to be familiar with the different types to know more about them. For example – ‘A dime a dozen’ – which means something which is very common. The use of this idiom in a sentence can be like “These red poppies are a dime a dozen which means that these red poppies are very common. If you separate these words, they will not have the same meaning as they did in the idiom.

METHODOLOGY

There are various uses of idioms and phrases. One common usage is to add color or emphasis to a sentence. Idioms and phrases can also be used for making a comparison. For example, “as busy as a bee” is an idiom that compares the busyness of a bee to how busy someone is. Idioms and phrases can also be used to make a point more forcefully, as in the idiom “beat around the bush”, which means to avoid speaking directly about a topic. ‘Idioms’ are said to have come from different stories in the past. They have metaphorical meanings. A phrase is a brief expression that has a meaning but cannot stand alone as a sentence. A phrase is a grammatical unit that is comprised of different words chained together. We have five types of ‘phrases’ in the English language: ‘noun phrases’, ‘verb phrases’, ‘adjective phrases’, ‘adverb phrases’, and ‘prepositional phrases’. Each phrase is determined by its head. Phrases do not have a subject and a verb and they also do not have complete meanings:

Listening to music → Noun phrase;

Go to the bathroom → Verb phrase.

A noun phrase is a group of words that have a noun or pronoun. It is used to modify the **noun**. In other words, it can be said that a noun phrase can function as a subject, an object, or a complement in a sentence.

- **My brother's friend** had come to visit him. (Used as a subject).
- **Scented candles** are my favorite. (Used as a subject).
- The students were asked to find **the buried treasure**. (Used as an object).

An adjective phrase or an adjectival phrase is a group of words that consists of an **adjective**. It can be used to complement it. It provides more information about the noun or pronoun in a sentence. In other words, it can be said that it functions just like an adjective in a sentence.

- Annu has **silky, smooth** hair.
- People, **living in large cities**, often find it difficult to reach in time.

An adverb phrase or an adverbial phrase is a group of words that includes an **adverb** and other modifiers. It performs all the functions of an adverb. It can be placed in any part of the sentence, with respect to the part of speech they modify.

- We are planning to finish our group project **by the end of May**.
- **Later this evening**, my cousins and I have planned to go to the park.

A verb phrase can be used just like a verb. It consists of a main verb and an auxiliary verb. For example, Students **are practicing** hard in order to participate in the state tournament.

A prepositional phrase consists of a preposition and an object. It works just like an adjective or an adverb. It relates the subject and the verb in a sentence. It is used to modify the nouns and verbs in a particular sentence.

For example, it was too hard for me to concentrate **with the kids jumping around**. The jewelry boxes were kept **inside the cupboard**.

This group of words has a meaning that is clear to the readers as there is no hidden meaning. A phrase is similar to a clause in a sentence though it stands hierarchically at a lower level than a clause.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There is indeed a great difference between idioms and phrases. Any idiom is a phrase but not every phrase is an idiom. As it was clear above, these two are completely different structures. So, they cannot be used interchangeably. It is important to note that an idiom is also a phrase. For example, let's look at the phrase, "raining cats and dogs". Here, this phrase does not actually mean cats and dogs are falling from the sky. It refers to heavy rain. These groups of words are not always used as idioms. They can be used as simple phrases as well. For example, "Finally, at the end of the lecture, he saw the light and realized how foolish his first assumption was. He saw the light of the lighthouse".

Idioms carry fixed meanings, whereas phrases do not have a fixed meaning. Idioms are units and the meaning cannot be understood by separating the words. For example, **A Piece of Cake**-A task that can be accomplished very easily. We are not talking about cake here. If we want to translate directly, we will make a mistake. Besides **All in The Same Boat** means that everyone is facing the same challenges.

On the other hand, the meaning of each word contributes to the meaning of the phrase. An idiom can only be understood when one knows the meaning, whereas a phrase can be easily deduced. Idiom is a linguistic tool that allows writers to say something in the garb of another. Idioms have a meaning that is different from the dictionary meaning of the individual words in the idiom. It is actually use of figure of speeches, to create a meaning that is different from the meanings of the individual words of the phrase. This is the reason why non-natives and other students of the English language find it hard to grasp the meaning of an idiom. Phrases are used by us in our daily lives in a functional manner whereas idioms are used for ornamentation of the language.

But until this time these terms in Uzbek linguistics are being mixed up, there are even confused thoughts. For example, "tarvuzi qso'zltig'idan tushdi" in the mother tongue textbooks of general secondary schools a phrase is called a phraseologism. This is actually not a phraseology. This is an idiom. Phraseologisms are related to things,

events, and events in society, while idioms do not have such a relationship,- explains the linguist Uzbek scientist G'.Salomov.

CONCLUSION

If idioms and phrases were the same things, they would not be called by two different names in Uzbek and world linguistics. Therefore, not understanding the difference between them, not paying attention to these aspects when applying them, and translating from one language to another will cause big mistakes. It can cause many problems, especially in the translation of artistic works.

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